

SOME FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AT PRIMARY SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the features and methods of teaching English to primary school students. The authors highlight specific features that the teacher should pay attention to and substantiate the importance of an individual approach to each school student.

Key words: methods of teaching English, individual approach, school, students

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In the modern world, the English language is no longer an individual desire of each individual person for self-improvement, but an everyday necessity determined by the needs of social life in society. Knowledge of English makes a job applicant more competitive and attractive compared to other candidates. The ability to communicate not only in your native language allows you to travel comfortably; English is one of the most effective communication tools; borrowings from it have enriched almost all languages of the world. Foreign language teaching should be carried out in Uzbek society from a very early age. Only in this case Uzbekistan will be able to compete with the most developed countries in the world in terms of education. It has long been proven that the later a child begins to learn English, the more difficult the learning process is, although this argument must be considered in terms of the individual abilities of each child [1, p. 55]. The result of any language education should be a formed linguistic personality, and the result of education in the field of foreign languages should be a secondary linguistic personality as an indicator of a person's ability to take full part in intercultural communication [3]. Within the framework of this article, it is proposed to consider the features and specific features that should be taken into account when teaching a foreign language to primary schoolchildren. A person's primary school age, when he is studying in primary school, is determined by the most important circumstance in a child's life - his admission to school. At this time, intensive development of the child's body occurs (central and autonomic nervous systems, activity of internal organs, etc.). In addition to the biological, there is an active mental development of the student's personality and the knowledge laid down by the teacher at this stage of development is the key to the student's effective perception of the educational and teaching process in the future.

In this regard, it is necessary to highlight the importance of the teacher's individual approach to the class. In addition to going through all stages of the established training program, the teacher's task is to identify the characteristics of each student's perception of the taught material, identify the reasons for the failure of a number of students and develop interest in learning English, which

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can be achieved, for example, by building a system of communication with students in a foreign language through application of the question-answer system. However, to achieve this goal, a special pedagogical system is required, the construction of which should be based on the principles of differentiation and integration, student-oriented orientation, and the developmental and activity-based nature of teaching [6, p. 40-46].

A foreign language as an academic discipline is very different from other subjects of the school curriculum, and thus, obviously, students have some difficulties in studying this subject [5]. The authors highlight the following as the most significant features of teaching English to primary schoolchildren: – during the period of study in primary school, abstract thinking has not yet been formed in schoolchildren. Children's attention is attracted by the objects and processes around them. In this connection, the specific topic of the lesson should be accompanied by visual accompaniment; – a foreign language is not a “native” language, the study of which is carried out throughout the entire period of a person's life, starting from childhood, which in turn requires the teacher to place special emphasis on memorizing the material taught as part of school lessons; – the teacher's task at the initial stage of introducing students to the English language does not aim to provide extensive knowledge in this area. At this stage, it is of greater importance to introduce schoolchildren to the English alphabet, teach them to establish sound-letter correspondences, master the means of expressive reading (intonation, pausing and logical stress, understand and comprehend the main facts of the text, corresponding to the age characteristics and interests of students, etc. - due to the specifics It is common for human memory to remember little things in detail at an early age. In this connection, English lessons should be accompanied by something special and memorable, associated with some significant events in the life of the class; – younger schoolchildren cannot concentrate their attention for a long time and fully during the entire lesson, therefore, the teacher must focus on the most important points of the topic covered. It would not be amiss to repeat the most significant moments of the lesson at the end of the lesson. A teacher working with younger grades must first of all create a favorable atmosphere during the lesson. This can be achieved by stimulating schoolchildren to actively participate in the lesson, while it must be taken into account that it is necessary to “play along” with students who initially behave inactively in class. One of the significant disadvantages of teaching children a foreign language today is the lack of attention paid to educational games. As O.M. points out. Shiyan, the game is mistakenly considered an episodic technique, and not the basis of all speech training, as required by the science developing today - acmeolinguistics [8]. The final learning results should be achieved not only by the victory of one or another student, but also, to a greater extent, by the game procedure itself, within the framework of which the process of assimilation of the taught knowledge is carried out effectively. In this regard, it is advisable to create linguistic classrooms in schools, equipped with teaching materials, layouts, and drawings, which makes working with children much more interesting and effective. The use of various games (including solving riddles, crosswords, dramatizing songs, poems, fairy tales) ensures children's constant interest in foreign language speech activities. At the same time, it is important not only how a student speaks a foreign language, but also what he says, whether the information expressed or perceived by ear has personal significance for him [2]. The teacher must first of all

determine for himself the purpose of a particular game moment, and based on this, give the students a clear instruction. The rules of the game must be correctly formulated and accessible to the child's understanding [4]. To consolidate the material covered, it is advisable to introduce something like testing at the end of the lesson. For example, structure a lesson in such a way that each student writes on paper or attaches pictures of subjects called by the teacher that were covered by the class during the lesson.

Bibliography:

- [1]. Alkhazishvili A.A. *Basics of mastering spoken English*. – *Enlightenment*, 1988.
- [2]. Voronina G.I., Soloutsova E.I. *Foreign languages in primary school*. – M.: Publishing house "New Textbook", 2003.
- [3]. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. *theory of teaching foreign languages: Linguodidactics and methodology: textbook. aid for students Linguistic univ i fak. in. language higher ped. textbook establishments*. – M., 2004.
- [4]. Zhabina I.V. *The use of role-playing games in teaching English grammar to primary school children // Materials of the International Youth Scientific Forum "Lomonosov-2011" / Responsible. ed. A.I. Andreev, A.V. Andriyanov, E.A. Antipov, M.V. Chistyakova*. – M.: MAKS Press, 2011.
- [5]. Zimnyaya I.A. *Psychology of teaching a foreign language at school*. – M.: Education, 1991.
- [6]. Kuznetsov A.A., Ryzhakov M.V. *Some aspects of developing the content of education at the senior level of school // Standards and monitoring in education*. – 2003. – No. 1.
- [7]. Putin V.V. *Development of additional education and higher school [Electronic resource] // Official website of the newspaper "Komsomolskaya Pravda"*. – Access mode: www.kp.ru (date of access: 02/13/2012). 8. Shiyan O.M. *Acmeolinguistic approach to teaching foreign languages*. – M., 1999.